

Social Anxiety Among Post Graduate Students In Relation To Gender And Streams Of Study

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Abstract

Due to Social Anxiety educational achievement was undermined & social life is impaired therefore the aim of the study was to investigate social anxiety in university students of different academic stream. Through purposive random sampling technique 200 students from 4 academic streams constituted sample for the study. 25 males & females from each stream were involved in the sample selected from the various academic streams of Pt.R.S.U. Raipur Chhattisgarh. Liebowitz Social anxiety scale (LSAS—SR. 1987) was used to assess social anxiety. The results revealed that the science students significantly show higher level of social anxiety in comparison to other mode of educational groups. Significant interaction of gender & stream on social anxiety was found. There was no significant difference found of gender on social anxiety. The result of the present study helps to identify the students of particular streams with high social anxiety. They can be helped to overcome the problems in social interaction.

Keywords

Adolescents, LSAS-SR (Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale), Gender, Social Anxiety, Stream & Educational Group.

Introduction

Social anxiety is uniquely western phenomena which investigated more in the north America, Australia & Europe. Anxiety not shown in particular situation or person unlike communication with others. it occurs in peer setting or any other age appropriate relationship. Social situations always provoke fear of anxiety viz. freezing, clinging, shrinking or failing to speak in social situations. It persists typically for 6 months or more. In DSM IV at the age of under 18 years it persists at least 6 months. There were not any direct physiological effects of a substance or another medical conditions attributed for fear, anxiety or avoidance. Rockille (2016). Lifetime prevalence of Social Anxiety Disorder found in DSM IV 9.5% in females and 4.9% in Males. Researches shows 4% to 8% adults from general population suffering from social anxiety. Behind this findings perfectionism and its elements procedure fear of negative evaluation presence which predicts high social anxiety in adults. Social stress starts from early days of life which proceeds into adulthood. However, Research shows that social anxiety is more prevalent in woman. (Kessler et al., 2005) Social anxiety has been studied in various genres. Shyness, Performance anxiety, Social phobia, Avoidant personality disorder, Social withdrawal, Social isolation, Public speaking anxiety, Speech anxiety, Communication apprehension, Fear of interpersonal rejection, Dating anxiety, Separation anxiety, Stage fright, fear of strangers, shame, embarrassment, social inhibition, social timidity. All of these & more fall under the umbrella of social anxiety. But there is Lacuna of studies which unfold the prevalence of social anxiety among post graduate students of various discipline. University students face many educational situations. At the same time, they get evaluated by others & become more worried, which affects many areas of their life, psychological, family, environment, health, mainly at the educational level, so it is necessary to study social anxiety of Post Graduate students of various study discipline. Academic achievement is influenced by a number of social and psychological factors mainly social anxieties and self-esteem influence academic achievement Ahmed (2019). Despite the difficulties social anxiety creates for sufferers, it is highly responsive treatment and its symptoms can be effectively managed.

Objective of study

1. To find out difference in social anxiety among students of different academic streams (Science, Arts, and Physical Education & Social Science).
2. To find out gender difference in social anxiety.
3. To study interaction effect of gender & different academic streams on social anxiety.

Review of Literature

Priya & Raj (2022). Conducted a study to find relationship between social anxiety and their negative self-portrayal in college going early adults. Through

the self-report of social anxiety scale and negative self-portrayal scale collected data analyzed by correlation and regression. In conclusion study denote a direct correlation where social anxiety is connecting to more with critical self-evaluation in various situations. In both the areas social anxiety or self-portrayal no significant difference was observed in gender bases, means male and female college students has a similar effect of social anxiety and self-portrayal.

The literature analysis provided by **Rejki, N. A. (2024)** was revealed the predictors which significantly increase social anxiety among early adult students includes: negative self-perception, students' self-esteem and support of family and others. Analysis of this study helps to understand that the various internal and external variables can influence the escalation of social anxiety among students.

Zhang, Ni, Xie, Xu & Liu., (2017). Investigate the gender difference among adolescents with social anxiety. 181 children and adolescents age of 10 and 14-year-old students participate in this study. Exogenous cueing task was used to measure subcomponents of attentional bias to threat (hypervigilance and difficulty in disengaging) among adolescents with social anxiety and for children social anxiety scale was used. Findings of the study shows that social anxiety is more ascendant in males.

Main Text

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Performance rate of Chhattisgarh students in social service center is not up to the expectation level. Thus it is important to study the social anxiety among the student which may be hindrance in their performance.

Sampling

Through purposive random sampling 200 students from 4 academic streams constituted. Sample of the study 25 males & females from each stream were involved. Sample selected from the various academic streams taken are Science, Physical education, Arts & Social Science stream of Pt.R.S.U. Raipur Chhattisgarh. Factorial research method is used as there are more than two Explanatory variables has been taken.

Tools Used

In this present study to measure Social Anxiety (LSAS-SR) Liebowitz Social anxiety scale, self-report version developed by Liebowitz, (1987) was used for data collection. Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale is four point Likert type scale consistb24 items in questionnaire a 24-item questionnaire. The scale is 4-point Likert-type scales ranging from 0 (None) to 3 (severe) for fear, and 0 (Never 0 %) to 3 (Usually, 67-100 %) for avoidance. LSAS had strong internal consistency as well as convergent and discriminant validity & internal consistency was $\alpha = .94$.

Statistics Used in the Study

The data obtained was put to statistical analyses with the help of SPSS version 16. To find out the effect of gender and Academic streams 2*4 ANOVA (Science, Arts, Physical Education, & Social Science) was computed.

The author first contacted the authorized person of the related departments with the permission of the authority and departmental Participants. Participants selected purposively in group of different study streams respectively science (Physics & chemistry); Social Science (history, psychology, economics and MSW); Physical education & Arts (Hindi, English & Sanskrit). The information obtained with the help of tools. A necessary instruction was given to the participants before the administration of the test and was told their participation was voluntary and their identity would remain anonymous. Respondents were convinced about confidentiality of the information and information will be used for research purpose.

Analysis

The results of descriptive statistics are Crosstab stream*SA*Gender was mentioned in Table 1. Chi-Square was reported in Table 1.1, Another descriptive statistic output of Mean & SD is reported in Table 2. Summary of ANOVA is reported in Table 3. Scheffe's post hoc test is reported in Table 4.

Table : 1
Crosstab: Stream* SA*Gender

Gender	Stream	SA						Total
		very severe SA	severe SA	marked SA	moderate SA	mild SA	absence of SA	
Male	SC	(5) 20.0%	(12) 48.0%	(6) 24.0%	(2) 8.0%	(0) 0.0%	(0) 0.0%	(25) 100.0%
	PhyEdu	(0) 0.0%	(0) 0.0%	(1) 4.0%	(6) 24.0%	(11) 44.0%	(7) 28.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Arts	(0) 0.0%	(0) 0.0%	(1) 4.0%	(8) 32.0%	(13) 52.0%	(3) 12.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Social Science	(1) 4.0%	(0) 0.0%	(2) 8.0%	(5) 20.0%	(14) 56.0%	(3) 12.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Total	(6) 6.0%	(12) 12.0%	(10) 10.0%	(21) 21.0%	(38) 38.0%	(13) 13.0%	(100) 100.0%
Female	SC	(0) 0.0%	(9) 36.0%	(0) 0.0%	(11) 44.0%	(5) 20.0%	(0) 0.0%	(25) 100.0%
	PhyEdu	(0) 0.0%	(0) 0.0%	(1) 4.0%	(7) 28.0%	(9) 36.0%	(8) 32.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Arts	(0) 0.0%	(1) 4.0%	(1) 4.0%	(9) 36.0%	(13) 52.0%	(1) 4.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Social Science	(1) 4.0%	(0) 0.0%	(3) 12.0%	(7) 28.0%	(9) 36.0%	(5) 20.0%	(25) 100.0%
	Total	(1) 1.0%	(10) 10.0%	(5) 5.0%	(34) 34.0%	(36) 36.0%	(14) 14.0%	(100) 100.0%
Total	SC	(5) 10.0%	(21) 42.0%	(6) 12.0%	(13) 26.0%	(5) 10.0%	(0) 0.0%	(50) 100.0%
	PhyEdu	(0) 0.0%	(0) 0.0%	(2) 4.0%	(13) 26.0%	(20) 40.0%	(15) 30.0%	(50) 100.0%
	Arts	(0) 0.0%	(1) 2.0%	(2) 4.0%	(17) 34.0%	(26) 52.0%	(4) 8.0%	(50) 100.0%
	Social Science	(2) 4.0%	(0) 0.0%	(5) 10.0%	(12) 24.0%	(23) 46.0%	(8) 16.0%	(50) 100.0%
	Total	(7) 3.5%	(22) 11.0%	(5) 7.5%	(55) 27.5%	(74) 37.0%	(27) 13.5%	(200) 100.0%

Table 1 shows that 5 Male students of Science stream found very severe anxiety & 12 were severe anxiety. Mild Social Anxiety presence in all academic streams and also shown in 36 females. In overall population there were 74 students both male & female found Mild social anxiety, 55 were moderate social anxiety, 5 were Marked and 22 were Severe category of social anxiety whereas 27 students not shown any kind of social anxiety symptoms.

Table:2
Chi-Square

	Value	df	Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	104.701 ^a	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	108.646	15	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	34.06	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 1.1 Chi-Square statistics value explain the significant difference between Stream & Social Anxiety. Table shows significant association between stream and social anxiety at (.05) significance level, highlights the significant difference in Stream & social anxiety ($\chi^2=104.701$, $df=15$, $P=.000$).

Table: 2
Mean & SD

Stream Gender	Science		Arts		Phys Edu		Social Science		Total	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Male	85.08	13.09	44.52	12.0	40.24	13.8	48.00	20.03	54.46	23.31
Female	64.88	17.82	49.20	13.1	39.64	14.6	47.08	19.20	50.20	18.58
Total	74.98	18.54	46.86	12.6	39.94	14.0	47.54	19.4	52.33	21.13

Table 1 reveals the mean value of the male students of science streams (**85.08**) & female students of the science streams (**64.88**). Mean value of the data showing that male & female students of the science stream have higher social anxiety & both male (**40.24**) & female students (**39.64**) of the Physical education stream have lower social anxiety. The total Mean value (**54.46**) of the data reveals that male students have higher social anxiety comparatively female students.

Figure 1

Figure 1 has shown the graph of the students of science stream having higher level of social anxiety.

Figure 2

Figure 2 has shown the graph male students having higher level of social anxiety of the science stream.

Table: 3
Summary of 2*4 ANOVA

No. of streams	Sum of Square (SS)	df	Mean Square	F value	significance
Gender	907.38	1	907.38	3.664	.057
Stream	35969.98	3	11989.99	48.419	.000
S*G	4481.98	3	1493.99	6.033	.000
Error	47544.88	192	247.63		
Total	636590.000	200			
Corrected Total	88904.220	199			

Table 3 reveals that The Significant F ratio for Academic streams (48.419), which is significant at level of (.05), indicates that Students of different academic streams differ in Social Anxiety. The F ratio for Interaction effect of Gender and Stream was (6.033) which is significant at the (.05) level indicates that there is significant joint effect of Gender and different academic streams but for Gender the significant F ratio is (3.664) which is not significant at the (.05) level, indicates that there is no significant difference was found in the mean of social anxiety for gender.

Table: 4
Post hoc test (Scheffe's Test)

S.No.	(I)Stream	(J)Stream	Mean Difference (I-J)	Mean	Std. Error	Sig.
1.	Science & Arts		28.12*	Science (74.98) & Arts (46.86)	3.147	.000
2.	Science & Physical education		35.04*	Science (74.98) & Phys Ed (39.94)	3.147	.000
3.	Science & Social science		27.44*	Science (74.98) & Social science (47.54)	3.147	.000
4.	Arts & Physical education		6.92	Arts (46.86) & Phys Ed (39.94)	3.147	.188
5.	Arts & Social science		-.68	Arts (46.86) & Social Science (47.54)	3.147	.997
6.	Physical education & Social science		-7.60	Phys Ed (39.94) & Social Science (47.54)	3.147	.124

Table 4 reveals the group difference in different academic streams & Post hoc test (Scheffe's test) was used to analyze whether the academic stream groups differ significantly in social anxiety results. Post ANOVA comparison test reveal that the

science students at (.05) significantly show higher level of social anxiety in comparison to other groups.

Result and Discussion

Results of the present study indicate that there is significant effect of streams in study on social anxiety of post graduate students. The students of Science stream have shown higher social anxiety comparison to the students of other stream. Symptoms of social anxiety is very common in university students but it varies in different level **Cooley (2007)** denoted in his study. **Fatma & Aqil (2017)** who found a significant difference between science and commerce streams in relation to their social anxiety and academics. Villiers (2019) found on his study that in Academic Environment of science stream student's high perfectionist traits are vulnerable factor for social anxiety also slight differences found in male and female's (53.4% Male; 47.6% Female) social anxiety. **Lal (2016)** also found a significant difference in students studying in different streams and there is insignificant interaction effect was found regard to social anxiety. In present study students are from science stream were showing highest level of social anxiety. Gender & different academic Streams effect collaboratively on social anxiety. Our hypothesis of the study that no significant differences between gender and social anxiety accepted but in mean difference it significantly shows higher in male students have higher social anxiety then females supported by (**Vitasari, 2010; Jun et al., 2013 & Abelli et al., 2015**) that males were more socially anxious, scrutinized & having social phobic traits consistent with behavior inhibition in comparison to females. In comparison to other streams male students of the science show higher level of social anxiety against with female students of different academic streams. **Alkhathami & et al (2014)** suggested to emphasize on male students for involving on social task in a specific culture in the context of their social anxiety. Perceived as less socially active incorporate social anxiety in males. Although some evidence exist that a remarkable proportion of post graduate students have social anxiety in some level varied by different academic streams.

Conclusion

Social anxiety is a rising social issue with life altering experience which also affect academic performance of the students. It is also a negative evaluation of self by others, which emerge in specific social situations. Environmental Influences and Stressful Life Experiences is also a significant Cause of Social Anxiety. Finding of the study giving a clear picture of social anxiety that the students of science stream having an anxious experience of being observed by others and how much difficulty they facing on the time of conversing with friends, strangers, or any type of authority figures. Stress made males more selfish and competitive, while females become other-oriented, cooperative and more generous. (Nickels et al.,2017). Female post graduate students having low social anxiety in comparison to male which may denote that females are more prone to deal with social situations as they less sensitive for their gender roles in the present era. whereas male students finding themselves less socialized. There is difference exist encounter at men and women's work associated with their social roles. (Cahoon et al., & menaghan et al., 1984). This study helps to develop insight for early detection and adequate intervention are crucial to reducing the overall burden of social anxiety among adolescents before it persist in early adulthood specially in particular stream viz., Science discipline.

Suggestions for the future Study

More data and observations with more reliable tools are needed for better future outcome while it's done with less resources. Some general localizations are not taken in these research should be studied on a broader perspective in different culture and different ethnicity.

Limitation of the Study

Inclusion Criteria

1. Stream with different subjects like physics, chemistry, history, psychology, physical Education & Language were comprising.
2. male & female post graduate students united for sample.
3. On the basis of regular attending, students are included for Research.
4. Sample considered from Raipur District.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Engineering & other vocational subject type streams were excluded.
2. School Students & Under graduate students were excluded.
3. University Dropouts & Private students Excluded.
4. Students having severe mental illness any critical Health Issues, Disability was excluded.

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